

WAYS OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE AND SOCIAL SUPPORT

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Abstract. This article explores the ways of preparing female students for family life and providing them with social support. It emphasizes the importance of integrating educational, psychological, and sociocultural approaches into the learning process to develop young women's readiness for family formation, responsible motherhood, and the balanced combination of professional and personal life. The paper also analyzes directions of state policy, pedagogical conditions, and practical mechanisms that contribute to the social protection and empowerment of female students.

Keywords: female students, family life, social support, gender equality, education, pedagogical approach.

This article analyzes the social and psychological factors of the formation of ideas about the family in students. The student period is an important stage that determines the individual's views on the family, the value system and psychological readiness. This article scientifically examines the influence of the social environment, the experience of the parental family, cultural values, the education system, the media and the peer group on students' ideas about the family. The adoption of the Strategy for Achieving Gender Equality by 2030 shows that the issues of women's rights and their social support are being considered at the official level. However, the issue of preparing female students for family life is a complex process that requires a systematic approach and the participation of educational and social institutions.

The process of social support and preparation of female students for family life in higher education institutions is carried out through the creation of an environment of gender equality, the integration of gender roles into curricula, the provision of psychological and social assistance, and the exchange of national and

international experience. The goal is to ensure equal development, overcome stereotypes and form stable family values based on equality, not on roles assigned by society. It is necessary to create an environment in which each student can realize his or her potential, regardless of gender, social background or other factors. At the same time, it is important to combat gender stereotypes in educational materials and teaching methods.

Curricula should include different points of view on gender, counter stereotypes and contribute to a more accurate reflection of social roles. Psychological support for students is of great importance, especially during the period of adaptation to the higher education system and at the stage of family planning. Within the framework of universities, it is possible to organize events that help students to better understand social and family roles based on the principles of gender equality. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, issues of ensuring gender equality are at the center of attention of state policy. At the national level, a consistent policy is being pursued in our country to comprehensively support women, expand their rights and opportunities. At the same time, large-scale work is being carried out in society to eliminate outdated stereotypes regarding the role of men and women in the family and social life. Reforms based on democratic values, along with ensuring human interests, are aimed at strengthening the status of women in society, protecting their rights and opportunities. In this regard, increasing the political, social and economic activity of women is one of the most important directions of state policy.

The fact that women are being entrusted with responsible leadership positions testifies to the high trust and respect of the head of state for them. Advanced foreign experiences are also being taken into account in ensuring gender equality in Uzbekistan. In recent years, important documents have been adopted in this direction, in particular: the Law “On Guaranteeing Equal Rights and Opportunities for Men and Women” (2019), the Law “On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence” (2019), and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of January 4, 2020 “On Measures to Improve the System of Protecting Women from Harassment

and Violence”. Targeted state programs are being implemented in the country to provide comprehensive social support to girls and women in difficult life situations. For example, in 2018–2020, approximately four thousand women in need of housing improvement were provided with initial payments from the Public Fund for Support of Women and Families. The State Employment Development Fund has also introduced a practice of allocating grants to cover the costs of vocational training for women from low-income families.

These measures have significantly expanded the social and economic activity of women, especially in rural areas. Ensuring equal rights and opportunities for men and women in the social, economic and political spheres is considered an important factor in strengthening the stability of society and the economic strength of the state. According to statistics, almost half of the country's population are women, and their share among the economically active population exceeds 46 percent. In the fields of health care, education and social services, women make up more than 70 percent of the workforce, which indicates their significant contribution to the development of the country's social infrastructure. The gender policy implemented in Uzbekistan serves not only to protect women's rights, but also to create broad opportunities for the realization of their scientific, professional and social potential. The development of social support and gender equality mechanisms is an important factor in the formation of a mature civil society and the modernization of the higher education system.

Research conducted by modern Uzbek educators and sociologists shows that increasing the role of women in society and professional life contributes not only to economic growth, but also to strengthening the institution of the family. According to N.Kh. Ergasheva, socio-economic support for women and the development of their leadership potential in higher educational institutions ensures the stability of the educational environment and helps to form relationships based on the principles of gender equality among young people. In recent years, important strategic documents aimed at supporting women and the family have been adopted in Uzbekistan. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

“On measures to further strengthen the institution of the family” (No. UP–6195, March 18, 2021) and the State Program “Year of Attention and Appreciation” (2024) [1] are among them. These documents define the priority areas of state social policy - the upbringing of youth and increasing the role of women in society. In addition, the introduction of gender-oriented programs in the higher education system allows not only girls, but also boys to form a sense of equality, mutual respect and responsibility for the future of society and the family. Higher educational institutions thus serve not only as centers of professional training, but also as an environment that forms a culture of family values based on the principles of equality and cooperation. This process is consistent with the tasks set out in the “Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan - 2022–2026”, which emphasizes the need to provide social support to women and create conditions for their active participation in economic, political and social life. Modern youth lives under the influence of a complex of social, economic and cultural factors that determine their worldview and life priorities. In the context of globalization and digital transformation of society, the issue of preserving spiritual, moral and family values is of particular importance. Therefore, preparing young people for independent work and family life is one of the urgent tasks facing the education system. As modern researchers note, pedagogical science does not yet pay enough attention to current sociocultural challenges in the formation of higher education graduates' readiness for family relationships and parental responsibility. Although the system of professional guidance at the school and college levels has developed, the issues of forming a culture of family relationships often remain on the sidelines of the educational process. At the same time, the growing influence of Western values, based on individualism and free forms of cooperation, has the opposite effect on traditional views on the family. As a result, family institutions are facing a crisis, the number of divorces is increasing, and the birth rate is decreasing. This situation is also reflected in sociological research in recent years. Such trends negatively affect the psychological state of young people, distorting their ideas about responsibility, love, and parenthood. Therefore, there is a growing need to create a pedagogical system

aimed at instilling in students a sense of respect for family values, the importance of marriage, responsibility for the future generation, and the preservation of cultural traditions. Preparing young people for family life is an integral part of the humanitarian mission of higher education and should serve the spiritual, moral, and social development of the individual. In conclusion, preparing students for conscious marriage and responsible parenthood is not only a pedagogical, but also a national task, requiring the combined efforts of educational institutions, family, and public organizations.

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